

REPORT:

A3.4.1: Literature survey on Microfluidic Bonding Strength

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A3.4.1 M6	METU, with the support of IPQ, INESC MN, RISE, LNEC and microfluidic will review in the literature the existing methods for testing the bonding strength of microfluidic devices manufactured and sealed by different means (e.g. silicon microchannels bonded to silicon or glass or thermoplastic microfluidic devices sealed by thermal bonding, ultrasonic welding, adhesive bonding). A report on the specifications for different materials will be written and shared to end-users and the relevant stakeholders.	METU , IPQ, INESC MN, RISE, LNEC, microfluidic

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1. Scope

As a critical step in the fabrication of microfluidic devices, bonding must securely seal the microchannels while maintaining control over channel deformation and surface wettability. This report reviews the current measurement methods used to measure the bonding strength, covering widely used techniques such as tensile, shear, peel, burst, and leak tests. It also covers the test setups, measurement parameters, and applicability of these techniques to different material combinations.

2. Introduction

In microfluidics, bonding is utilized to seal the open microfluidic channels that are patterned on a substrate, using a secondary plain substrate, to create a leak-proof structure. Alternatively, other approaches, such as femtosecond laser ablation or additive manufacturing can be used to create embedded microchannels directly, or an open-channel design can be used to eliminate the need for sealing.

Although early microfluidic devices were either in silicon/glass (Terry et al., 1979) or all glass (Colyer et al., 1997; Effenhauser et al., 1993; Jed Harrison et al., 1992; McClain et al., 2003) fabricated using lithography based microfabrication techniques, thermoplastics have subsequently emerged as an attractive, often more economical, alternative for many microfluidic applications. Polymer substrates such as polystyrene (PS), cycloolefin copolymer (COC), cycloolefin polymer (COP), and polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) offer advantages including high optical transparency, low cost, chemical resistance, mechanical strength and biocompatibility. Various sealing techniques have been employed across different materials and fabrication methods to enclose microchannels.

The most commonly used methods for assessing bond strength include tensile, shear, and burst-open tests (Lu et al., 2024). Tensile and shear tests provide general measures of bonding performance, whereas burst and leakage tests offer application-specific evaluations. However, burst and leakage tests often yield results that depend strongly on channel geometry (Giri & Tsao, 2022). Peel tests, in turn, are highly sensitive to sample geometry and therefore frequently yield data that are difficult to compare across studies (Mata et al., 2005). Furthermore, although universal testing machines (UTMs) are standard for ISO-based materials testing, they may not provide reliable results for microfluidic devices due to a lack of suitable fixtures. This highlights the need to identify a repeatable, comparable and metrologically verifiable protocol for measuring bond strength (Jia et al., 2004).

2.1. Bonding Strength Measurement and Test Methods for Microfluidic Devices

This section reviews widely adopted test methods for evaluating bonding strength in microfluidic devices. Each method is described in terms of its measurement approach and the fundamental testing principles. Bonding strength test methods are classified according to the taxonomy proposed by Lu et al. (Lu et al., 2024), with the descriptions adapted and expanded for this study.

2.1.1. Mechanical Bond Strength Tests

2.1.1.1. Tensile Testing

In tensile testing, the chip is held in place by the top and bottom grips of a tensile testing machine. A fixture ensures that the load is transferred perpendicular to the bond interface. During the test, the machine pulls the top and bottom layers in opposite directions, forcing the bond interface to separate while recording the maximum load at rupture. The bonding strength (σ) is calculated as follows:

$$\sigma = \frac{F_{N,max}}{A} \quad (1)$$

where $F_{N,max}$ is the maximum normal force recorded at the instant of bond failure and A is the bonded surface area. Figure 1 illustrates the tensile testing method.

Figure 1: Illustration of the tensile test method (Lu et al., 2024).

2.1.1.2. Crack Opening (Double Cantilever) Test

In the crack opening method, a wedge (typically a razor blade) is inserted between the bonded substrates to form a crack of a specific width. The width of the crack (L) is related to the bonding strength and surface energy γ (in mJ/m^2) based on the following relationship (Fan et al., 2014):

$$\gamma = \frac{3000}{16} \frac{t_b^2}{(1/E_1 d_1^3 + 1/E_2 d_2^3) L^4} \quad (2)$$

where E_1 and E_2 are the elasticity moduli of the substrate materials, d_1 and d_2 are the thickness of the substrates, t_b is the wedge thickness, and L is the width of the crack. Figure 2 illustrates the crack-opening test.

Figure 2: Setup for crack-opening method (Fan et al., 2014).

This method, along with the corresponding equation relating crack length to bonding strength, was originally developed to assess the bonding of silicon wafers (Maszara et al., 1988; Vallin et al., 2005). Subsequently, the method was adopted for testing thermoplastic microfluidic devices (Fan et al., 2014).

2.1.1.3. Shear Testing

In shear testing, a lateral force is typically applied parallel to the bonding interface using a universal testing machine. During the test, both the applied lateral shear force and the resulting displacement are recorded. The bonding shear strength (τ) is related to the force according to:

$$\tau = \frac{F_{s,max}}{A}$$

where τ is the shear bonding strength, $F_{s,max}$ is the maximum recorded shear force, and A is the overlapping interface area of the bonded substrates. This method is therefore also referred to as a lap shear test.

Shear testing can be carried out using a standard universal testing machine (also used for tensile testing) by configuring the grips to apply force in shear mode. Figure 3 illustrates the shear test.

Figure 3: Conventional single-lap shear testing system setup (Lu et al., 2024)

2.1.1.4. Peel Testing

Peel testing is utilized when microchannels on a rigid substrate are sealed by a thin film, or when two thin films (one of which accommodates the microchannels) are bonded to each other. In such cases, a tensile or shear test is not feasible, therefore peel tests provide more representative results (Borók et al., 2021; Giri & Tsao, 2022; Lu et al., 2024). During the test, the sample is peeled at a specific angle to observe the separation behaviour between the film and the substrate or between two films. Bonding strength is calculated by recording the applied force and the peel distance.

Peel tests are generally performed in three different geometric configurations:

- 180° peel test: The thin film is peeled off at a 180° angle from its fully adhered state to the substrate. In this setup, the substrate is usually fixed, and the film is pulled upwards. The maximum force value at which rupture occurs during the peeling process is recorded.
- 90° peel test: The film is peeled off at a 90° angle, perpendicular to the substrate surface. This test is particularly suitable for flexible materials and allows for more accurate observation of the force change during separation.
- T-peel test: Used in systems where two thin film layers are bonded together. Both ends of the sample are held and the layers are separated in a T-shape. Force fluctuations throughout the peel are recorded and bond strength is generally evaluated based on the average peel force.

Figure 4 illustrates different configurations of the peel test.

Figure 4: Setup for (a) 180°-, (b) 90°-, and (c) T-peel testing

2.1.2. Fluidic Integrity Tests

2.1.2.1. Leakage Test

The leak test is a very basic and practical method of assessing bond quality. This test can be carried out under no-flow or flow conditions. In the former case, a liquid – preferably dyed (Do et al., 2023; Trinh et al., 2020) or fluorescent (Chueh et al., 2007) to enhance optical contrast – is dispensed into the microchannel and left for a specific period. At the end of the test period, the microfluidic device is inspected optically to check for any leakage. However, as the test period extends, evaporation at the ports or other external effects may interfere with the results (Trinh et al., 2020). In the case of a leakage test under flow conditions, the liquid is forced to flow continuously through the microchannel. Flow rates are set such that the volume injected per unit time is a multiple of the microchannel's internal volume (Zhang & Lee, 2015). Thus, this ratio can be utilized as a measure of quality to assess the bond. This method is more relevant to the operational reliability of microfluidic devices operating under continuous flow. Other leakage tests developed for microfluidic devices based on optical inspection or the use of flow and pressure sensors are described in the technical report by van Heeren et al. (van Heeren et al., 2022) and in MFMET I deliverable 1 (Daugbjerg et al., 2023)

2.1.2.2. Burst Pressure Test

Burst pressure testing is one of the most widely used functional testing methods for evaluating the bond strength of microfluidic structures. Roughly, in this method, a liquid or gas is pumped into the microchannel at a gradually increasing pressure until delamination, leakage or sudden bursting occurs at the bond interface. To ensure pressure builds up in the microchannel, all ports other than the pressure inlet port can be plugged (Hasan et al., 2023). A pressure control setup, involving a pump and a regulator is needed to provide a controlled pressure input. During the test, either the pressure or the flow rate is monitored to identify the pressure at which bursting occurs, as a sharp drop in pressure (Kratz et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2024) or a non-zero flow rate (McMillan et al., 2020; McMillan et al., 2021) indicates bond failure. However, detecting small leaks may require highly sensitive sensors. Thus, the setup could be supported by optical detection to enable more precise detection of the onset of failure.

3. State of the Art Review

The previous section provides an overview of the principles of the bonding strength measurement methods. This section reviews the state of the art in the application of these methods, with a particular focus on the mechanical bond strength tests.

3.1. Tensile Testing

The development of a tensile testing method to determine the bonding strength of thermoplastic microfluidic assemblies has been addressed. This method relies on universal testing machines to apply controlled uniaxial loading (Huang et al., 2024; Sözmen & Arslan Yildiz, 2021; D. Sun et al., 2015; Tennico et al., 2010). Reported protocols use fixtures such as a metal extension (Huang et al., 2024), or an extension made from the same material as the microfluidic device (D. Sun et al., 2015). This extension is bonded to the sample with epoxy resin to ensure uniform load transfer. The bond areas are clearly defined, enabling direct calculation of tensile strength by normalizing the failure force. Loading rates remain low and quasi-static, typically 0.5 mm/min or 1 mm/min (Huang et al., 2024; Sözmen & Arslan Yildiz, 2021; D. Sun et al., 2015), in order to minimize artefacts dependent on the rate. The loading rate can be as low as 0.06 mm/s (Tennico et al., 2010).

Tensile testing is a direct method for quantifying interfacial bond strength. It offers a more straightforward implementation than fluidic integrity methods, such as burst testing. The consistent use of universal testing machines, low crosshead speeds and standardized bonding geometries highlights a convergent methodological approach within microfluidic bonding research. However, the extensions used to grip the samples are not standardized, and the epoxy-mediated interface between the sample and the extension may introduce variability that is not intrinsic to the bonded microfluidic layers themselves. This lack of standardization can affect load distribution and potentially bias the measured tensile strength.

3.2. Crack Opening Testing

Crack-opening tests evaluate bond integrity by inserting a thin wedge between two adhered polymer layers and quantifying the resulting delamination length. Reported implementations typically involve the use of metal blades or shims of a known thickness, which are inserted into the bonded interface of thermoplastics such as PMMA, PS or PC. The bonding strength is then inferred from the crack length or delaminated area that is measured (Cao et al., 2015; Fan et al., 2017; Persson et al., 2022; Song & Park, 2017; Tsao et al., 2007).

Although the method is conceptually simple and enables a comparative assessment of bond quality, most studies provide limited methodological detail regarding the mechanics of wedge insertion, placement accuracy or the configuration of optical measurements. This lack of standardized reporting introduces uncertainty in the comparability of crack-opening results across studies. Furthermore, (Persson et al., 2022). reported on their method for determining the separation length, enabling reproducible quantification. Figure 5 illustrates the measurement configuration used by Persson et al. (Persson et al., 2022).

Figure 5: Image illustrating how the wedge and the crack length can be related in crack opening test (Persson et al., 2022)

3.3. Shear Testing

Shear and lap-shear tests are widely used to quantify the bonding strength of thermoplastic microfluidic assemblies. Most studies employ standard mechanical testing equipment operated at relatively low, controlled crosshead speeds (El Fissi et al., 2015; Faghih & Sharp, 2018; Madadi et al., 2023; Mahmoodi et al., 2019; Roy et al., 2012; Song & Park, 2017). Shear testing has been performed using universal testing machines (El Fissi et al., 2015; Madadi et al., 2023; Roy et al., 2012; Song & Park, 2017) or rheometers equipped for tensile loading (Mahmoodi et al., 2019). Crosshead speeds have varied by more than two orders of magnitude, from 0.1 mm/s (Mahmoodi et al., 2019) and 0.5 mm/min (Madadi et al., 2023; Roy et al., 2012) to 1 mm/min (Faghih & Sharp, 2018) and 10 mm/min (El Fissi et al., 2015; Song & Park, 2017). This variation indicates an absence of a unified testing rate, despite all studies aiming to characterize nominally similar interfacial properties. Despite this, all studies rely on the same fundamental principle: applying a controlled shear load to an overlapped joint until failure, after which the maximum load is normalized by the bonded area. This demonstrates that shear testing remains a practical method for assessing bond quality in microfluidic device fabrication. Figure 6 illustrates the typical shear testing setup.

A common limitation of all reported lap-shear protocols is that the specimens are intentionally fabricated with an extended unbonded section to enable direct gripping in the testing machine. Real microfluidic devices, by contrast, are uniformly bonded across their entire surface area and lack these dedicated gripping regions. Consequently, standard lap-shear geometries cannot represent fully bonded chips, and the absence of grippable extensions means that actual devices cannot be tested directly. Therefore, applying lap-shear testing to real microfluidic assemblies would require a dedicated fixture to hold the fully bonded device without altering its geometry. This would ensure appropriate load transfer and a representative shear stress distribution.

Figure 6: Shear test setup illustrating how the sample is mounted between the jaws of the testing equipment (Oyama et al., 2020).

3.4. Peel Testing

In the T-peel configuration, two flexible substrates overlap over a defined region. Peeling is imposed at the joint by pulling the free ends in opposite directions. Mahmoodi et al. (Mahmoodi et al., 2019) prepared T-peel specimens from thin PMMA films with a defined overlap and applied tensile loading at a speed of 0.1 mm/s using a rheometer. Sun and Besser (P. K. Sun & Besser, 2020) used a comparable geometry, defining the test area as $10 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ and

reporting adhesion as force normalized by sample width ($\text{N}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$). These studies demonstrate that T-peel testing is suitable for flexible thermoplastic laminates in which stable, symmetric peeling can be achieved. Figure 7 shows a typical T-peel test setup.

For microfluidic devices incorporating dissimilar or partially rigid substrates, 90° -peel configurations provide controlled peeling at a fixed angle. Khashayar et al. (Khashayar et al., 2016) evaluated tape adhesion to COC and glass using a 90° -peel test on a bond-testing instrument and maintaining perpendicular alignment, expressing peel strength as steady-state force per width (N/mm). Ganser et al. (Ganser et al., 2018) applied a similar protocol on a tensile tester using a custom jig and a crosshead speed of $1\text{ mm}/\text{s}$ to ensure consistent conditions. These methods demonstrate that angle-defined peel tests enable the reproducible assessment of interfacial toughness in device-relevant laminate structures, in which flexible–rigid combinations require controlled geometry to isolate the adhesive contribution.

Figure 7: Image showing flexible sheets gripped in T-configuration for peel testing (Mahmoodi et al., 2019).

3.5. Limitations of Current Bonding Strength Test Methods

All mechanical testing methods except the crack opening test can be performed using a universal testing machine. However, these methods have limitations in terms of their application. For example, peel-off tests are sensitive to microfluidic channel geometry, which means they cannot provide comparable data across studies (Kratz et al., 2020). Furthermore, the widespread unavailability of suitable fixtures to secure microfluidic devices, especially during tensile and shear testing, is a significant limitation. Conversely, efforts are being made to eliminate the need for complicated fixtures to secure microfluidic devices in mechanical tests. Kratz et al. proposed a transmission device that is compatible with glass slide-formatted microfluidic devices and translates compressive forces into shear and tensile forces (Kratz et al., 2020).

3.6. Standards and Parameters in Bonding Strength Test Methods

The tensile testing procedures for bonded thermoplastic microfluidic devices are partly based on ASTM D882 (Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Thin Plastic Sheeting) (ASTM, 2018) and ISO 527-3 (Plastics — Determination of tensile properties — Part 3: Test conditions for films and sheets) (ISO, 2018). These standards provide guidance on specimen geometry, gripping configurations, and environmental conditions. For bonded microfluidic chips, the dominant parameter governing measurement accuracy is tensile speed. Despite its

widespread use, tensile testing has some limitations in practice: custom fixtures are required to secure chip substrates, and the method is not suitable for multilayer devices containing more than two bonded layers.

Crack-opening tests also rely on several sensitive parameters that affect the derived bond strength based on surface-energy. These include the thickness of the blade used to initiate delamination, the time allowed for stabilization of the crack propagation, the length of the crack- and the polymer elastic modulus. Any variability in these factors is directly reflected in the calculated adhesion energy values.

Although there is no specific microfluidic standard, shear testing of thermoplastic microfluidic bonds is usually based on ASTM D732 (Standard Test Method for Shear Strength of Plastics by Punch Tool) (ASTM, 2024) or ISO 14129 (Fibre-reinforced plastic composites — Determination of the in-plane shear stress/shear strain response, including the in-plane shear modulus) (ISO, 1997). The punch-shear configuration defined in ASTM D732 is commonly employed, whereby samples are clamped in a shear punch fixture, and a punch is driven through the specimen at a controlled rate using a universal testing machine. This method facilitates stable gripping and enables reliable evaluation of interfacial shear strength. Key parameters include the definition of the overlap or punch area and control of the loading rate.

Peel test procedures for flexible or elastomeric microfluidic devices are usually based on either ASTM D6862 (Standard Test Method for 90° Peel Resistance of Adhesives) (ASTM, 2011) or ASTM D903 (Standard Test Method for Peel or Stripping Strength of Adhesive Bonds) (ASTM, 1998). T-peel configurations, which are widely used for flexible laminates, follow either ISO 11339 (Adhesives — T-peel test for flexible-to-flexible bonded assemblies) (ISO, 2022) or ASTM D1876 (Standard Test Method for Peel Resistance of Adhesives - T-peel Test) (ASTM, 2008). Accurate measurement depends on maintaining a constant peel angle and speed. More information on bonding strength method can be found in MFMET I deliverable 1 (Daugbjerg et al., 2023)

4. Conclusions

The review reveals that, despite the existence of a wide range of methods for assessing bond strength in microfluidic devices, none provides a universal solution that is suitable for all materials, geometries and device architectures. Mechanical tests such as tensile, shear, peel and crack-opening tests each address different aspects of interfacial integrity. However, the outcomes of these tests are strongly influenced by specimen geometry, fixture design, and loading conditions. Reported implementations also vary substantially in terms of test speed, clamping strategy and measurement procedure. This complicates comparison between studies and prevents the direct translation of results between different device designs.

The absence of standardized fixtures for microfluidic chips, the sensitivity of peel and crack-opening tests to sample geometry and the requirement for additional components, such as extensions or fixtures, all highlight the gaps in the field. While several standards can be adapted to some extent, they were not specifically designed for microfluidic devices and therefore do not address the unique mechanical constraints posed by bonded microchannel networks, thin substrates, or multilayer assemblies.

Taken together, these findings highlighted the need for consistent, microfluidics-specific testing standards that define sample preparation, fixture requirements, loading protocols and data analysis procedures. The establishment of such standards would facilitate reproducible testing, enable quantitative comparisons across fabrication methods and materials, and enhance the reliability of bond quality evaluations in both research and industrial settings.

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